

6 cases of thoracic-lumbar fracture-luxations: a retrospective study demonstrating the advantages of preoperative mri and use of 2-0 Unilock implants

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INTRODUCTION

This retrospective study includes 5 dogs and 1 cat that suffered thoracic-lumbar fracture-luxation. The objective is to illustrate how a preoperative MRI contributes to the decision-making process as well as to demonstrate the advantages of using 2-0 Unilock implants in such cases.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials - This retrospective study includes cases of five dogs and one cat: a 2-year-old Eurasian, a 3-year-old English setter, a 4-month-old Brittany, an 11-year old Yorkshire, a 14-year-old Ratier and a 1-year-old European cat. They all had been injured and presented with thoracic-lumbar fracture-luxations associated. Four of the cases were associated with a pelvic fracture and 1 case with a tail fracture. Four animals were paraparetic with preserved nociception and one dog was paraparetic with loss of deep nociception during medical stabilization. In all cases, there was instability with crepitus during mobilization of the spine.

Method - The six animals were medically stabilized and complete thoracic and abdominal imaging was performed. Spinal injury assessment included two orthogonal radiographs and an MRI. The injured areas were Th11-12 (1 case), Th12-13 (2 cases), L2-L3 (3 cases including the cat). On the radiographs, we noted axial displacement in 80% of the cases⁵ and displacement in the dorsal-ventral direction in 100% of the cases⁶. We observed a facet joint fracture in 1 case and an associated parcellar fracture of the vertebral endplate in 2 cases in L3 (including the cat).

The MRI examination showed the presence of extradural compressive material in 2 cases, deformation of the spinal cord in 4 cases, and an absence of hyperintense lesions on T2-weighted sequences of the spinal cord in all cases. Intervertebral disk lesions on the T2-weighted sequences were noted in all cases. These lesions allowed us to assess instability.

Surgical treatment with a thoracic approach and a ventral approach to the spine was done in 3 cases, while a lateral approach to the lumbar spine was used in 3 cases. Extradural compressive material was present in 2 cases and justified two mini hemi-laminectomies. Reduction was maintained with the help of a pin passing through the two vertebral bodies in 2 of the 3 thoracic cases. A 1-mm facet joint screw was added in the cat to maintain the reduction.

In all cases, primary contention was achieved using a 5-hole Unilock 2mm plate (with different thickness) with 2 locking screws placed in each vertebral body. A single standard cortical screw (1/24) needed to be placed due to the proximity of intervertebral space in the Yorkshire. Out of the 24 screws used, 21 were mono-cortical (87%). The plate was modeled in 4 cases.

RESULTS

We classified our results in 3 categories:

– Immediate post-operative results

Post-operative radiographs showed good reduction and presence of all the implants in the vertebral bodies. MRIs performed immediately post operatively revealed the decompression of the spinal cord and no violation of the vertebral canal by the implant in all cases.

The presence of the implants did not impede the assessment of the spinal canal and cord, and only the pins produced minor paramagnetic artefacts.

– Radiological follow-up.

We followed up at 3 weeks and 6 weeks and observed no loss of reduction, no plate breakage, nor any pin migration. However, there was loosening of 1 locking screw out of 24 (4.1%) in a thoracic site, which had no clinical consequence.

– Neurological recuperation.

Recuperation for 4 dogs and 1 cat proved to be excellent (normal locomotor function), while it was unsatisfactory for 1 dog (severe ataxia, but with recuperation of an ability to stand).

CONCLUSION

The objective of presenting this series is to illustrate the use of 2-mm Unilock implants for treating thoracic-lumbar trauma, which to our knowledge has not been done before. Unilock implants have been used successfully to stabilize cervical fracture-dislocations and caudal cervical spondylomyelopathy¹.

A recent study compared the rigidity of the 2.4-mm Unilock system with a locking steel implant and PMMA-screw combination on a C3-C4 model³. It did not demonstrate any significant difference in resistance. We did not have the concern of implant breakage.

We chose to privilege the use of locking mono-cortical screws. It has been shown that fixation of these screws is equivalent to bi-cortical pins used in the cervical spine². The primary advantage is limiting the risk of vascular trauma and spinal canal intrusion.

This risk is particularly elevated in the thoracic region, where the proximity of major vessels and very reduced implantation corridors⁴ justify a ventral approach. The latter also allows for better assessment of the reduction.

In this series of cases, none of the screws penetrated the spinal canal, and 87% of them were mono-cortical. The use of locking implants presents undeniable advantages, including limitation of plate modeling, which is difficult in this region; preservation of the reduction; and better fixation via the creation of a plate-screw unity at a stable angle. Ninety-six percent of the implants we used were locking implants, with only one cortical screw being necessary to provide satisfactory anchoring in the vertebral body. Only one implant loosening was noted on a locking screw.

We were able to evaluate the adaptability of this implant in patients weighting from 4 kg to 40 kg. The distance between the holes in the plate allowed us to place 2 screws per fragment. Titanium causes no paramagnetic artifacts, which allowed us to follow-up with an MRI.

The initial MRI examination determined the necessity of a spinal canal approach, which was done in 2 cases. For these two cases, the articular processes were preserved when the canal was opened. It seemed necessary to us to preserve the structures that remained stable.

The MRI also enabled more precise assessment of the instability than the radiographs without use of stress views involving risk. Indeed, in the established 3-compartment model, the intervertebral disk appears to be an essential element in rotational stability. The dorsal part is attributed to the intermediary compartment, while the central and ventral parts are attributed to the ventral compartment. As⁵ suggests, we consider that any case of full damage to the disk visible on the MRI renders the spine instable and is an indication to proceed with surgical stabilization.

We attach great importance to hyperintense medullary lesions on T2-weighted sequences for their prognostic value, even though this correlation has not yet been proven in the case of spinal fracture-luxations in dogs and cats.

Clinical relevance - The 2-0 Unilock implant seems both mechanically and structurally adapted to the treatment of thoracic-lumbar fracture-luxations and is a solid alternative to the use of PMMA. Pre-operative MRI examinations allowed us to assess instability, the presence of spinal cord injury, and the presence of extradural compressive material.

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